

COMPONENT PARTS AND TASKS OF PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS

Norqobilova Rayxona Davlatovna
TerDPI Theory of Primary Education
teacher of the department

Abstract: Information about the purpose of pedagogical diagnostics, the main functions and principles of pedagogical diagnostics, types of pedagogical diagnostics, teacher activity and diagnostic activity is provided.

Key words: pedagogical diagnosis, experimental, diagnostic, experimental, formative, student's potential, effective knowledge fund (thesaurus), generalization of thinking, learning in learning) pace of development.

The goal of pedagogical diagnostics is to determine, evaluate and analyze the progress of the pedagogical process in a timely manner in relation to the effectiveness of the latter.

In general, the tasks of pedagogical diagnostics:

- 1) optimization of the pedagogical process (assessment of the quality of education, training or management, identification of strengths and weaknesses in the work of the educational institution);
- 2) ensuring the correct determination of educational outcomes (education, management) based on the interests of society and individuals;
- 3) minimization of pedagogical errors based on the selected criteria;
- 4) to help students and teachers in the educational institution to form uniform pedagogical positions and requirements;
- 5) to support the organization of self-education of students and professional self-development of teachers.

If we focus on the tasks of a specific teacher or group of teachers, then we can distinguish the following tasks of pedagogical diagnostics:

1. Determination of the state of development of the relevant property.
2. To determine the dynamics of its development and changes in a certain period of time.
3. Establishment of real changes that occurred under the influence of organized educational influences.
4. Determination of prospects for the development of features (quality).
5. Taking into account the achieved development results, dividing subjects (children or groups) into categories for more differentiated work with them.
6. Development of recommendations (for a child or a group of children).
7. Determining the child's talent, inclinations, and individual abilities in order to take measures to develop them in time.
8. Comparative analysis of their developmental impact in order to develop recommendations for improving the developmental function of various education and training systems.

The main functions and principles of pedagogical diagnostics can be distinguished:

Diagnostic functions:

1. Feedback function.
2. The function of evaluating the effectiveness of pedagogical activity.
3. Educational and motivational function.
4. Communicative and constructive functions.
5. Information function.
6. Predictive function.

Diagnostic principles:

1. Objectivity;
2. Systematic;

3. Visibility (publicity);
4. Brevity;
5. Complexity of methods;
6. Strength.

The pedagogical diagnostic procedure is similar to the psychodiagnostic algorithm. The following stages of pedagogical diagnosis can be distinguished:

1. Determination of research goals and objectives.
2. Selection of criteria and indicators to determine the effectiveness of the phenomenon under study.
3. Choosing learning methods.
4. Preparation of diagnostic tools.
5. Learning topics.
6. Processing and interpretation of research results.
7. If necessary, discuss and analyze the results.

Types of pedagogical diagnostics can be classified as follows:

1. According to the main object of recognition: a) didactic (educational); b) educational; c) management.
2. By duration: a) short-term; b) longitudinal (continued).
3. According to the consistency criterion: a) episodic (situational); b) systematic. Longitudinal diagnostics of the system is called "monitoring".
4. According to the character of expression of results: a) quality; b) quantitative (quantitative measurements in pedagogy, as well as the department of pedagogical diagnostics that studies them is called pedagogical qualimetry).
5. By observation time: a) initial (entry); b) intermediate (repetitive); c) final
6. By size: a) complete; b) partially.

Diagnostic methods:

1. Non-experimental (serves to determine the presence or absence of a certain psychological characteristic) -

- questioning;
 - analysis of activity products;
 - tracking,
 - conversation.
2. Diagnostic (for quantitative measurement) -
- scaling,
 - distance,
 - sociometry,
 - testing.
3. Experimental (to explain mental phenomena) -
- laboratory,
 - natural,
 - modeling experience.
4. Formative (to identify development opportunities) -
- analysis,
 - prediction,
 - result message.

In addition, there is a study diagnosis, ie. outcomes, results achieved and learning. Diagnostics is given a wider and deeper meaning than traditional testing of students' knowledge and skills. The test only reports the results without explaining their origin. Diagnostics examines the results in connection with the ways and means of achieving them, reveals trends, dynamics of formation of educational products. Diagnostics includes monitoring, checking, evaluating, collecting statistical data, analyzing them, determining dynamics, trends, forecasting further development.

Diagnostics of education is inseparable from diagnostics of learning, because the correct idea of the achieved results can be obtained only in connection with the conditions of their achievement.

Learning is the student's ability to master the given content of learning. The most important components of the educational concept are:

1. potential opportunities of the student;
2. fund of effective knowledge (thesaurus);
3. generalization of thinking;
4. the rate of progress in learning (mastery of knowledge).

Learning - is achieved during the diagnosis of the level (level) of the intended learning goal.

General principles of educational diagnostics: a) impartiality; b) systematic; c) democracy.

A modern school should have no formal control. It is necessary and useful for didactic control to become a unique method of teaching and to have a clear education, a development direction, to be combined with self-control, especially for the student himself. should be. Diagnostic results to which value ratings (scores) can be applied contribute to self-determination of the individual (personal rating), which is an important motivating factor in a competitive society.

Teacher activity and diagnostic activity are inseparable. Diagnostics is of great importance in the purposeful and effective implementation of the educational process. This makes it possible to improve the process of education, training and development of children by controlling (monitoring) and correcting the entire system of education and training and its components.

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